

1 Additional material

Table 1: Median values and 68% confidence intervals for parameters from the `pyaneti` analysis.

Parameter	Unit	Value	Prior
Input stellar parameters			
$M_\star$	($M_\odot$)	$1.05^{+0.03}_{-0.03}$	
$R_\star$	($R_\odot$)	$1.31^{+0.03}_{-0.03}$	
T_{eff}	(K)	6005^{+50}_{-50}	
$v_{\text{rot}} \sin i_\star$	(km s^{-1})	2.5 ± 2.5	
J_{mag}	(mag)	8.196 ± 0.020	
Fitted parameters			
T_0	(BJD_{TDB})	$2177.4046^{+0.0026}_{-0.0028}$	$\mathcal{G}[2177.40, 0.01]$
P	(days)	$3.73659^{+0.00044}_{-0.00047}$	$\mathcal{G}[3.74, 0.01]$
$e \sin \omega$	($^\circ$)	$-0.10^{+0.21}_{-0.16}$	$\mathcal{U}[-1, 1]$
$e \cos \omega$	($^\circ$)	$0.20^{+0.11}_{-0.16}$	$\mathcal{U}[-1, 1]$
b	($^\circ$)	$0.847^{+0.034}_{-0.042}$	$\mathcal{U}[0, 1.2]$
$\rho_\star$	(g cm^{-3})	$0.672^{+0.93}_{-0.096}$	$\mathcal{G}[0.66, 0.1]$
$R_p/R_\star$	($^\circ$)	$0.0198^{+0.0014}_{-0.0012}$	$\mathcal{U}[0, 0.1]$
K	(m s^{-1})	$5.31^{+0.38}_{-0.37}$	$\mathcal{U}[0, 100]$
Derived parameters for planet TOI-2458 b			
M_p	($M_\oplus$)	$13.31^{+0.99}_{-0.96}$	
R_p	($R_\oplus$)	$2.83^{+0.20}_{-0.18}$	
e	($^\circ$)	$0.087^{+0.062}_{-0.056}$	
ω	(deg)	$-26.0^{+57.8}_{-41.8}$	
i	(deg)	$84.03^{+0.45}_{-0.52}$	
a	(au)	$0.0482^{+0.0025}_{-0.0027}$	
depth	(ppm)	$391.8^{+55.3}_{-46.3}$	
RM	(m s^{-1})	$0.31^{+0.12}_{-0.11}$	
Received irradiance	($F_\oplus$)	$865.0^{+98.8}_{-77.9}$	
Transmission spectroscopy metric ¹	($^\circ$)	$44.0^{+10.7}_{-8.1}$	
$\rho_\star^2$	(g cm^{-3})	$0.659^{+0.051}_{-0.047}$	
T_{eq}^3	(K)	$1509.4^{+41.4}_{-33.2}$	
T_{tot}	(hours)	$2.13^{+0.13}_{-0.14}$	
ρ_p^4	(g cm^{-3})	$3.23^{+0.76}_{-0.69}$	
g_p^4	(cm s^{-2})	1645^{+319}_{-293}	
g_p^5	(cm s^{-2})	1632^{+264}_{-236}	
Jeans Escape Parameter ⁶	($^\circ$)	$23.56^{+2.54}_{-2.40}$	
Parameters for planet TOI-2458 c			
T_0	(BJD_{TDB})	$2168.39^{+1.85}_{-1.72}$	$\mathcal{G}[2183, 7]$
P	(days)	$16.553^{+0.059}_{-0.061}$	$\mathcal{G}[16.6, 1.4]$
$e \sin \omega$	($^\circ$)	$0.04^{+0.28}_{-0.32}$	$\mathcal{U}[-1, 1]$
$e \cos \omega$	($^\circ$)	$0.45^{+0.17}_{-0.36}$	$\mathcal{U}[-1, 1]$
K	(m s^{-1})	$2.63^{+0.48}_{-0.48}$	$\mathcal{U}[0, 100]$
Derived parameters for planet TOI-2458 c			
$M_p \sin i$	($M_\oplus$)	$10.22^{+1.71}_{-1.90}$	
e	($^\circ$)	0.29 ± 0.16	
ω	(deg)	$4.3^{+48.1}_{-41.1}$	
a	(au)	$0.129^{+0.002}_{-0.002}$	
Other parameters			
q_1	($^\circ$)	$0.43^{+0.36}_{-0.28}$	$\mathcal{U}[0, 1]$
q_2	($^\circ$)	$0.37^{+0.30}_{-0.25}$	$\mathcal{U}[0, 1]$
u_1	($^\circ$)	$0.44^{+0.36}_{-0.31}$	$\mathcal{U}[0, 1]$
u_2	($^\circ$)	$0.14^{+0.39}_{-0.31}$	$\mathcal{U}[0, 1]$
Sys. vel. HARPS RVs	(km s^{-1})	$0.0016^{+0.0049}_{-0.0041}$	$\mathcal{U}[-0.5, 0.5]$
Sys. shift HARPS S-index	($^\circ$)	0.1544 ± 0.0012	$\mathcal{U}[-0.5, 0.5]$

Sys. shift HARPS H α	($\text{\AA}$)	$2.15^{+0.24}_{-0.20}$	$\mathcal{U}[-0.5,0.5]$
RV jitter	(m s^{-1})	$1.67^{+0.35}_{-0.29}$	$\mathcal{U}[0,5]$
Transit jitter	($\text{\AA}$)	0.0005144 ± 0.0000032	$\mathcal{U}[0,0.005]$
GP parameters			
A0 (RV)	(km s^{-1})	$0.0084^{+0.0053}_{-0.0040}$	$\mathcal{U}[-0.5,0.5]$
A1 (RV)	($\text{km s}^{-1}\text{d}$)	$-0.051^{+0.031}_{-0.045}$	$\mathcal{U}[-0.5,0.5]$
A2 (S-index)		$-0.0007^{+0.0024}_{-0.0030}$	$\mathcal{U}[-0.5,0.5]$
A3 (S-index)		$-0.123^{+0.053}_{-0.065}$	$\mathcal{U}[-0.5,0.5]$
λ_e	(days)	$74.7^{+17.6}_{-25.7}$	$\mathcal{U}[1,100]$
λ_p		$3.10^{+1.24}_{-1.18}$	$\mathcal{U}[0.1,5]$
P_{GP}	(days)	$47.97^{+6.96}_{-4.02}$	$\mathcal{U}[40,60]$

Comments: 1 - based on the equation from [Kempton et al. \[2018\]](#),
2 - from stellar parameters, 3 - based on the equation from [Kempton et al. \[2018\]](#),
4 - from K and $R_p/R_\star$, 5 - from planetary parameters,
6 - based on the equation from [Fossati et al. \[2017\]](#)

Table 2: Relative HARPS radial velocities and activity indicators of TOI-2458.

Date (BJD)	RV (m/s)	σ_{RV} (m/s)	Hα	S-index
2459626.57046	-3.60580	1.74066	1.06960	0.15825
2459627.57121	0.45331	1.63245	1.07206	0.15971
2459628.52387	9.23207	1.30024	1.07443	0.15460
2459628.59374	8.08026	1.46562	1.07478	0.16047
2459629.52190	5.98527	1.24333	1.07262	0.15703
2459629.59192	3.80151	1.46576	1.07208	0.16234
2459630.52217	-4.23015	1.24629	1.06989	0.16065
2459630.56781	-4.25610	1.14161	1.07355	0.15881
2459630.58519	-4.79558	1.15478	1.07014	0.15796
2459631.52037	0.00000	1.33286	1.06902	0.15526
2459631.58935	2.23137	1.30985	1.07101	0.15920
2459632.52137	6.28987	1.26168	1.07227	0.15689
2459632.60050	3.26533	1.33886	1.06858	0.16014
2459633.52765	-5.03571	1.34001	1.07016	0.15679
2459633.60602	-7.18474	1.51795	1.06998	0.15860
2459634.52241	-7.48829	1.57321	1.06951	0.15818
2459634.60253	-9.21190	1.61501	1.06998	0.15735
2459636.51653	0.96106	1.23570	1.07155	0.15686
2459636.59387	-0.08565	1.32675	1.06968	0.15648
2459637.51561	-4.62772	1.40295	1.07042	0.15445
2459637.59235	-7.00802	1.69053	1.07368	0.16017
2459638.51472	-6.17653	1.22186	1.07361	0.15664
2459639.54902	1.42886	1.39532	1.07361	0.15683
2459640.51211	-1.84278	1.70393	1.07007	0.16079
2459641.51016	-8.19887	1.30513	1.07639	0.15843
2459642.50970	-9.35474	1.54382	1.07154	0.15811
2459643.51141	-0.79903	1.46698	1.07540	0.15463
2459644.50853	-3.35652	2.04471	1.07520	0.14964
2459645.50755	-7.06186	1.75046	1.07355	0.14731
2459646.50805	-3.38800	1.55573	1.07195	0.15289
2459647.50417	0.40703	1.50461	1.07209	0.15054
2459648.50484	-6.72600	1.27400	1.07290	0.15213
2459653.53430	-5.78354	1.54562	1.07807	0.14714
2459657.50361	-5.01645	1.39315	1.07207	0.14690
2459657.53415	-6.14540	1.53096	1.07699	0.14837
2459658.49814	2.95163	1.45863	1.07256	0.14987
2459659.49560	-0.19182	1.56236	1.07232	0.14801
2459660.49647	-3.01936	1.57569	1.07350	0.15198
2459661.49501	8.11929	1.52942	1.07258	0.14718
2459662.49028	13.95170	1.69995	1.07152	0.14842
2459664.52268	-3.64051	1.36848	1.07040	0.14676
2459665.48892	6.66790	1.36021	1.07136	0.15873
2459666.52975	3.12895	1.60524	1.07196	0.15846
2459668.48463	-3.76043	1.61613	1.06904	0.15566
2459670.48430	-0.90826	1.56124	1.06785	0.16045
2459671.49321	-1.32617	1.35500	1.07331	0.15665
2459672.48851	-2.25176	1.60849	1.07266	0.15310
2459674.47901	0.67112	1.48633	1.07033	0.15450
2459675.47852	2.34194	1.56661	1.06851	0.15729
2459677.48053	10.91969	1.50582	1.07440	0.15440
2459678.47977	-0.61313	1.69065	1.07390	0.15629
2459680.47754	10.76232	2.11955	1.07010	0.15827
2459681.47464	8.98306	1.82464	1.06534	0.15895

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Date (BJD)	RV (m/s)	σ_{RV} (m/s)	Hα	S-index
2459682.47761	-5.07983	1.91448	1.06723	0.15419
2459685.48173	0.63113	1.60358	1.06884	0.15533
2459891.76265	6.06616	1.21894	1.07393	0.15666
2459893.73163	14.80380	0.84291	1.07371	0.15849
2459898.70094	5.79629	1.20872	1.07310	0.15829
2459900.74072	3.32741	1.69840	1.06977	0.15519
2459901.79418	5.58911	1.06385	1.07311	0.15309
2459902.72177	-0.96515	1.50172	1.07380	0.15649
2459904.71755	6.31906	1.61721	1.07318	0.15806
2459906.74864	-0.56126	1.62528	1.07719	0.15355
2459907.70776	6.29759	1.79251	1.07733	0.15792
2459908.72213	10.87003	2.18669	1.07902	0.14902
2459909.75548	6.43331	1.29718	1.07080	0.15772
2459927.66966	12.34636	2.11303	1.07640	0.15161
2459929.67684	-5.51379	1.79868	1.06982	0.15410
2459931.72420	-2.06245	1.78946	1.06959	0.15507
2459936.59670	-6.77609	1.69414	1.07239	0.15140
2459940.56949	-6.34509	1.57602	1.07320	0.15196
2459948.72207	0.43391	1.70429	1.07507	0.15224
2459972.56829	6.36334	1.39499	1.07297	0.15641
2459975.60344	2.94834	1.47080	1.07454	0.15427
2459978.64380	-5.00263	2.13103	1.07260	0.15359
2459981.59711	-1.95722	2.25326	1.07387	0.15369
2459983.64077	3.23188	2.27755	1.07863	0.14415
2460017.54799	0.59316	2.02706	1.07640	0.15167
2460019.54102	-5.88262	1.82536	1.07755	0.15345
2460021.53921	0.67872	1.53177	1.07248	0.15617
2460025.52714	3.98090	1.57371	1.07558	0.15725
2460029.49171	3.00734	1.90912	1.07559	0.14690
2460033.49697	-3.12350	1.60431	1.07157	0.15176
2460035.48864	2.72208	1.81145	1.06996	0.15296
2460178.88692	-0.42893	2.66881	1.07621	0.15933
2460215.85413	1.04048	2.23979	1.07201	0.15809

Figure 1.1: Correlations between the main free parameters of the `pyaneti` model from the MCMC sampling. At the end of each row is shown the derived posterior probability distribution.